

EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN LECTURE CLASSES OF THE SOIL SCIENCE COURSE

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Annotation.

The article describes some modern methods, their description and application issues that are suitable for conducting lectures on the soil science course.

Key words.

educational technology, unconventional methods, method, lecture, question and answer, brainstorming, strategy.

INTRODUCTION.

The main goal of the reforms being carried out in our country is to create a healthy and well-educated generation in our country with high spiritual and moral qualities.

The future of Uzbekistan, its prospects, first of all, depends on the education of young people, their healthy upbringing, education in the spirit of national ideals, national ideology and loyalty to the motherland. one of the urgent tasks. Fundamentally reforming the education system in Uzbekistan, raising it to the level of modern requirements, raising a mature generation for the future has become a priority of state policy.

These cases testify to the relevance of studying and analyzing the educational and training processes carried out in higher educational institutions in the example of the science of soil science in all theoretical and practical terms, and the high demands placed on the individual, i.e. mature, intellectual, creative For this activity in the education of personality, the wide use of modern pedagogical technologies is recommended in the course of the lesson.

MAIN PART.

Usually, in soil science, the technologies related to students' cooperation and group work mainly give important results in seminar classes, and during lectures, the teacher makes it possible to interest the student, concentrate his attention, accelerate the thinking process, and make it easy to learn. it would be appropriate

to use the organizer and technologies that can be tested by the teacher and repeat the acquired knowledge quickly. Below, we will first focus on the technologies of lecture classes [1-5].

"Brainstorming" method is a method that collects free thoughts and opinions expressed by students on a problem and comes to a certain solution through them. Developed by Alex Osborne (USA) in 1930. There are written and oral forms of the "Brainstorming" method. Each of the learners verbally expresses their opinion to the question posed by the teacher in oral form. Learners express their answers clearly and concisely. In the written form, students write their answers to the given question on paper cards in a short and visible way. Answers are attached to the board (using magnets) or pinboard (using pins). In the written form of the "Brainstorming" method, there is an opportunity to group the answers by certain characters. This method, when used correctly and positively, teaches a person to think freely, creatively and non-standardly. When using the "Brainstorming" method, it is possible to involve all learners, including the culture of communication and discussion among learners. Learners develop the ability to express their thoughts not only verbally, but also in writing, and the ability to think logically and systematically. The lack of evaluation of the expressed opinions leads to the formation of different ideas among students. This method serves to develop creative thinking in students. The "Brainstorming" method is implemented depending on the goal set by the teacher:

1. When the goal is to determine the basic knowledge of learners, this method is implemented in the introductory part of the lesson.

2. Repetition of the topic or connection of one topic with the next topic is carried out in the transition to a new topic.

3. When the goal is to strengthen the topic, it is done after the topic, in the reinforcement part of the lesson.

Basic rules for using the "Brainstorming" method:

1. Expressed opinions are not discussed and evaluated.

2. Any opinions expressed will be considered, even if they are not correct.

3. Every learner must participate.

Below is the structure of the "Brainstorming" method.

The structure of the "Brainstorming" method

The stages of the "Brainstorming" method are as follows:

1. Students are asked a question and they are asked to give their answers (opinion, idea and reasoning) to this question;
2. Learners express their opinions on the question;
3. Students' ideas are collected (on a tape recorder, videotape, colored paper or blackboard);
4. Ideas are grouped by certain signs;
5. A clear and correct answer to the above question is selected.

Advantages of the "Brainstorming" method:

Failure to evaluate the results leads to the formation of different ideas among students;

All learners participate;

Ideas are visualized;

There is an opportunity to check the basic knowledge of learners;

It makes students interested in the subject.

Disadvantages of the "Brainstorming" method:

Failure of the teacher to ask the question correctly;

A high level of listening ability is required from the teacher.

Lecture teaching, unlike other forms of education, in traditional education is mainly directed by the teacher, and this situation is not able to attract all the students, their teaching materials are unevenly taught. can lead to many such

defects [6-10]. Therefore, conducting the study of lecture data on the basis of their cooperation with the teacher, as well as on the basis of the organization of mutual cooperation, ensures the active participation of each student in the lesson process and thereby promotes their mastery at a high level. allows to provide. As such technologies, the use of "question-answer" and "Blitz-survey" methods in teaching lectures on the soil science course is highly effective.

"Question - answer" method. The method helps to determine the level of mastery of the subject by students. The effectiveness of its application depends on the fact that the questions and answers are expressed in a clear, concise and understandable way, and are relevant to the topic.

The application of the method in the educational process is carried out in the following order:

"Blitz survey" method. "Blitz-survey" (English "blitz" - quick, instant) method is considered a method that requires short, clear and concise answers to the given questions. In educational institutions, questions according to this method are mainly asked by the teacher. The answers to the given questions can be returned collectively, in groups, in pairs or individually. The form of the answer is determined according to the type of training, the complexity of the subject being studied, and the coverage of the pupils (students) [11-14].

The teacher draws up questions that require the disclosure of the essence of the studied topic and certain components and brings it to the attention of the students.

Pupils (students) answer the given question clearly and concisely in a short period of time

When working in a group (pair), one student answers the given question (his group mates fill in the answer (however, thoughts should not be repeated)

form of images (tables, diagrams).

CONCLUSION.

Thus, methods such as the above, which are new in the teaching of soil science and lead students to think continuously during the lesson, have a high impact on their independent thinking and drawing conclusions, and lead to a high level of mastery of lecture classes.

There are usually many non-traditional educational technologies that are suitable mainly for seminar classes. However, in the lecture, the teacher is in the lead role and should use only methods specific to the process. When using the above-mentioned methods, firstly, the teacher acts as a leader, and secondly, he constantly engages students and makes them think independently and continuously.

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